

Vulnerable Road Users Accident Prevention via Smart City Data Fusion: Experimental Evaluation of a 5G MEC Architecture

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Abstract—Enhancing the safety of Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) poses a significant research challenge in the context of connected mobility and a plethora of technological opportunities trying to balance efficiency and widespread applicability. This paper presents a VRUs’ safety application focused on applying 5G Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC), commercial mobile devices, public cellular networks, and data fusion between vehicle positioning and city camera infrastructure. The application showcases the designed system and its experimental evaluation in the Modena Automotive Smart Area (MASA) through an experimental 5G MEC infrastructure to build a secure and efficient connected mobility environment.

Index Terms—Smart City, Vulnerable Road Users, 5G, Edge Computing

I. INTRODUCTION

Ensuring the safety of vulnerable road users (VRUs), such as pedestrians, cyclists, and motorcyclists, is a crucial aspect of intelligent mobility [1]. Traditional Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication systems have been utilized for vehicle-infrastructure communication [10], but their reliance on short-range technologies limits their effectiveness in supporting a wide range of VRUs [2], [11]. In this paper, we focus on leveraging Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) solutions [13] and edge 5G connectivity to investigate new solutions to support VRUs in road safety. Our approach explores an alternative by utilizing public cellular connectivity, which offers a broader coverage and seamless connectivity to enable enhanced support for VRUs by integrating multiple data sources, including vehicle GPS positioning data and the Smart City smart camera infrastructure.

The designed system (schematically illustrated in Figure 1) operates within the context of the Modena Automotive Smart Area (MASA¹), a dedicated testing area located in Modena, Italy, which provides a realistic environment for the development and testing of innovative automotive and mobility solutions and applications. MASA consists of real city streets augmented with intelligent mobility infrastructures and services.

The main goal of the application is to notify a user about possible collisions between him/her and other road users. The location and movement of the person using the application

is tracked via a GPS-enabled device (e.g., smartphone). The locations and trajectories of all the other road users are extracted from the smart cameras installed in the area. Once the application predicts a possible collision, it sends an alert to the user. For example, a driver can be notified by the application about pedestrians’ jaywalking. Or a distracted user (jaywalking while looking at the smartphone) can be notified of an approaching vehicle.

The fact that the application uses smart cameras, typically installed on poles – and thus having a clear/unobstructed view of the street segment, notably improves road users’ recognition, allowing the detection of users hidden from the user perspective (e.g., a VRU jaywalking behind another car or bus).

Of course, one of the main constraints of this application is the end-to-end delay (i.e., latency) from the cameras *seeing* a dangerous situation to the alert being shown to the user. This end-to-end delay is the result of computation time (e.g., video processing, collision forecasting) and communication time to send data from the smartphone to the application server and vice versa and from smart cameras (and intermediate servers) to the application server.

In this work, we focus on communication delay and extend the MASA infrastructure by integrating a new Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) layer. This MEC layer plays a crucial role in enabling real-time data integration from multiple sources and provides processing and analytics capabilities at the network edge. The experimental MEC infrastructure, deployed in proximity to the MASA area, ensures 5G network coverage with low latency and high bandwidth. MEC services are connected to the MASA infrastructure via MQTT, facilitating the exchange of mobility metadata and alerting messages.

Overall, this paper presents two main contributions:

- 1) We present a novel system and application to support VRUs’ safety by forecasting possible collisions among road users.
- 2) We evaluate the application by analyzing the critical aspects of latency and responsiveness of the application, with a focus on the impact of MEC technologies over standard Cloud-base solutions.

In the following of this paper we present background and related work focusing on VRU application in smart city and

¹MASA: <https://www.automotivesmartarea.it>

Fig. 1: An application running on a smartphone, or any GPS-equipped device, sends location and mobility information to an applications server. The application server receives data about other road users’ locations from the smart cameras. The application server predicts possible collisions and notify the user accordingly.

MEC-based optimization (Section 2). Then we present the architecture of our application, its main components and communication protocols (Section 3). In Section 4, we presents experiments and results. Finally, Section 5 concludes and present future works.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

In the realm of smart cities, the integration of advanced technologies to enhance the safety and mobility of Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs)—including pedestrians, cyclists, and motorcyclists—has garnered significant attention. Several studies have explored the deployment of intelligent transportation systems (ITS) to mitigate accident risks and improve mobility for these groups. For instance, the awareness messages generated by vehicles and VRUs have been studied in [10], while the work in [12] emphasizes the role of Vehicle-to-Infrastructure (V2I) and Vehicle-to-Pedestrian (V2P) communication in alerting drivers to the presence of VRUs, thus reducing collision probabilities. Additionally, systems utilizing machine learning algorithms to predict pedestrian movement patterns and potential crossing behavior have been shown to significantly decrease the likelihood of accidents [14]. These predictive models, often implemented through real-time data analysis from city-wide sensor networks, provide timely alerts to both VRUs and drivers. Furthermore, advancements in augmented reality (AR) and wearable technologies offer promising avenues for enhancing VRU safety. Devices such as smart helmets and AR glasses can provide cyclists with real-time navigation assistance and hazard warnings [3]. This not only aids in safe route planning but also in dynamic hazard

avoidance. Moreover, the integration of AI-driven traffic signal systems that adapt to the presence of VRUs has been shown to improve the safe mobility experience in urban areas [9]. These systems prioritize pedestrian crossings and extend signal durations when detecting high VRU traffic, thereby reducing wait times and exposure to moving vehicles. Collectively, these technologies underscore a comprehensive approach to safeguarding VRUs by leveraging the synergy between connectivity, real-time data analytics, and intelligent infrastructure within smart cities.

From a more technical perspective, a number of works show that the synergy between Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) and 5G technology is pivotal in significantly reducing network latency, thereby enhancing mobility and accident prevention systems. MEC, by bringing computation and storage resources closer to the data source, and 5G, with its high bandwidth and low latency capabilities, can collectively transform urban transportation networks. Research in [4], [5], [17] underscores the effectiveness of MEC in processing data at the network edge, which drastically minimizes latency and enhances real-time decision-making capabilities crucial for mobility applications. This real-time processing capability is instrumental in accident prevention systems where milliseconds can be the difference between a near-miss and a collision. For example, the work in [8] demonstrates the integration of MEC with 5G to create an ultra-reliable, low-latency communication environment, enabling real-time vehicle-to-everything (V2X) interactions. Such interactions facilitate instantaneous hazard warnings and adaptive traffic signal controls that respond dynamically to vehicular and pedestrian flows, thus reducing accident risks.

Moreover, MEC and 5G are central to the development of advanced driver assistance systems (ADAS) and autonomous driving technologies. According to [20], the combination of these technologies allows for rapid data exchange between vehicles and roadside infrastructure, enabling precise localization, timely hazard detection, and swift maneuvering decisions. These capabilities are particularly beneficial in complex urban environments where quick reaction times are critical. Furthermore, MEC’s ability to process vast amounts of data at the edge supports AI-driven analytics for predictive modeling of traffic conditions and accident probabilities, as highlighted [15]. These models provide actionable insights that preemptively adjust traffic flows and enhance VRU safety.

The implementation of MEC in conjunction with 5G also facilitates the deployment of smart traffic management systems that are more responsive and efficient. Research in [19] illustrates how these systems can leverage edge computing to dynamically manage traffic signals, prioritize emergency vehicles, and reduce congestion, all of which contribute to safer and more efficient urban mobility. Additionally, the low latency provided by 5G ensures that these adjustments are made in real-time, enhancing the overall effectiveness of traffic management strategies. In essence, the integration of MEC and 5G technology forms the backbone of a responsive and intelligent urban mobility framework that prioritizes safety and

Fig. 2: MASA Area with Smart Cameras and the VRU application developed and experimentally evaluated in the target area considering both the mobile interface and the in-vehicle led notification solution.

efficiency, paving the way for smarter and safer cities.

III. APPLICATION DESCRIPTION

As already introduced, we designed and developed an application that serves as a key component of our VRU's alerting service. Installed on the driver's vehicle, this application is responsible for sending real-time GPS positioning data, visualizing a map with detected VRUs, and receiving alerts generated by the algorithm running on the MEC infrastructure on the target geographic area illustrated in Figure 2a. We developed two versions of the client application:

- a mobile web-based application utilizes modern web technologies to provide a user-friendly interface and seamless interaction with the system [1]. It enables the driver to access important information and receive timely alerts regarding potential collision risks. Figure 2b shows the graphical interface of our app, designed for the end user with few distractions. Even at this early stage of the designed system, the conducted field tests demonstrate the demo's capability to accurately identify and alert potential collisions, as shown in Figure 2d. The successful low-latency combination of multiple city-level data in real-time, along with the notification system, validates the effectiveness of the first stage of our approach in a real-world scenario, enhancing driver awareness and contributing to collision prevention in smart city environments without requiring dedicated network infrastructure or onboard hardware.
- an embedded computing version (using a Raspberry Pi with a 5G-GPS hat) connected to an addressable led strip to provide a more direct and unobtrusive experience for the driver, see Figure 2c.

Videos of both the implementation and prototype of VRU applications and experiments have been made available on [6]). To support the application on the server side, we extended the MASA infrastructure by integrating a new Multi-Access

Edge Computing (MEC) layer. This MEC layer plays a crucial role in enabling real-time data integration from multiple sources and provides processing and analytics capabilities at the network edge. The experimental MEC infrastructure, deployed in proximity to the MASA area, ensures 5G network coverage with low latency and high bandwidth. MEC services are connected to the MASA infrastructure via MQTT, facilitating the exchange of mobility metadata.

The overall architecture can be divided into two types of subsystems based on their location: the MEC Area and the Edge Area, both located within the MASA.

MEC Area. The upper area in Figure 3 is the MEC area. MEC stands for "Multi-Access Edge Computing" and is a computational area ideally located near the base station (BTS). The MEC server enables the lowest possible latencies because data packets no longer need to travel to a server via the Internet. This is crucial for critical applications like this one. In practice, the MEC server can be located even hundreds of kilometers from a BTS, but it's connected with high-bandwidth optical fiber, minimizing latency. Within the MEC area, we have deployed an MQTT Broker and our Algorithm that can predict collisions and generate alerts.

- *MQTT Broker:* The main communication hub, the MQTT Broker, allows clients to communicate their positions to the algorithm and receive alerts. MQTT is a fast, scalable, and reliable protocol designed for IoT applications. It's widely supported by IoT devices and other types of applications running on servers or smartphones. Web applications are the only exception. In this case, bidirectional WebSocket communications [18] are established to allow connected devices (e.g., vehicles) to send GPS positioning data and receive alerts. However, in these cases, we can also integrate and bridge MQTT communication through WebSocket, with the aim of effectively covering all types of applications that can interact with our system,

Fig. 3: Schematic representation of the proposed application's architectural design with MEC and MASA infrastructures, the involved protocols, connected Smart Cameras, and end users devices such as smartphones, vehicle on-board units, and IoT assets.

particularly with respect to web clients.

- **VRU Algorithm:** The newly designed VRU algorithm is executed on the MEC layer, combining heterogeneous data to identify potential collision risks between vehicles and nearby VRUs. By comparing and estimating their directions based on received data, the algorithm detects potential collision scenarios and generates alerts for involved entities in the target geographic area. As a first step, the algorithm detects newly connected users to the system and initiates a new thread specifically for that user. Within the algorithm, optimizations are made to limit the number of operations, ensuring low execution times. An example is using Redis, a fast and scalable database supporting spatial queries, to check for potential collisions only with nearby objects and road users. Each device is associated with a user to allow redundancy of information. For example, a single user can have a 5G smartphone displaying information about their surroundings and a GPS tracker on their bike that can send an alert if necessary. Another example is a car driver: the user's smartphone can actively send location data, while the car can also be a connected device that communicates its position and receives alerts from the

system, offering redundancy for the car's safety systems. In these scenarios, all devices associated with a user are managed by a single thread.

MASA Area. The MASA area, as can be seen in the lower part of Figure 3, is primarily filled with cameras that monitor street activity. These cameras can be of two types: CCTV cameras and 5G Smart cameras.

- **CCTV Cameras:** These are existing cameras installed by the municipality for security purposes. They typically transmit a video feed to a central recorder. However, in our architecture, we also connect to these cameras to use the video feeds for analysis. This Video Processing Node is equipped with a custom Machine Learning algorithm that outputs the position, direction, speed, and type of object or user. This metadata is published to an Edge MQTT Broker instance that's bridged with the instance inside the MEC to keep both synchronized. This allows devices using data on the MEC Broker to be aware of the metadata processed by the Video Processing Node on Edge and published on the Edge Broker.
- **5G Smart Cameras:** Unlike CCTV cameras, these are "smart" because they can perform some computation onboard. This allows for local video feed analysis, reducing latency caused by data transmission. These smarter cameras only output metadata that can directly feed the Broker inside the MEC thanks to their ability to access the 5G mobile network.

The MASA area is also equipped with internal processing nodes that execute the video processing algorithms for CCTV cameras and provide another instance of the MQTT broker on edge.

- **Video Processing Node:** Video streams from smart cameras are processed by edge nodes for local video analysis, object detection (e.g., vehicles, buses, motorcycles, bicycles, and pedestrians), and generation of anonymous metadata adhering to privacy and GDPR [7] regulations. These metadata are transmitted to the MASA data center using the MQTT protocol [16] to build and maintain a centralized vision of city mobility patterns.
- **Edge MQTT Broker:** The Edge MQTT Broker is the main broker for the entire system, although it may not be the most utilized one as end devices rely on the MEC MQTT Broker. However, it's essential not only for cameras but also for having a central point for multiple MEC areas in the future. This central point enables seamless device migration between different MEC areas and also hosts future applications that don't require the lowest latency and can be independent of the specific MEC area.

Finally, from the connectivity and security perspectives, all devices are connected to either a 5G or 4G LTE radio network, and the first server they encounter is the MEC server, even before reaching the internet. Therefore, for IoT devices, internet access can be disabled for the highest security.

Fig. 5: Raspberry Pi RTT results with respect to Cloud and MEC deployment of target services.

Fig. 6: Tablet RTT results with respect to Cloud and MEC deployment of target services.

average value and the distribution of the samples in both scenarios, while the final pair of illustrated results, (c) and (f), show the distribution of the delay samples and the count of measurements for each delay value. From these graphs, it is evident that there is a significant percentage improvement in communication delay when the service is deployed on the MEC. This is corroborated by both the sample distribution and the average value, which is on average $22.5ms$ for the MEC deployment compared to the average value of $50.6ms$ for the Cloud deployment.

An interesting observation arises when combining Figure 5

with Table I, despite the significant mean RTT reduction, the standard deviation is almost the same. In other words, graphs (d) and (e) closely resemble a shift down of graphs (a) and (b), respectively, while graph (f) closely resembles a shift left of graph (c). More specifically, the worst-case delays are high in both configurations, being an order of magnitude higher than the standard deviation, imputing the worst-case delayed source to the access network and not to the service location. Indeed, excluding a few sample groups from graph (a) with worst-case delay higher than $300ms$, the pattern and the density of worst-case delay samples are similar between graphs (a) and

Fig. 7: Mobility Results in the target MASA experiments area with respect to the RTT values using the Raspberry Pi testing node. Three different delay thresholds have been identified to group samples and measurements with respect to Cloud and MEC Services to visually understand the impact of the RTT on different application requirements.

(d).

A similar analysis and the associated MEC-cloud comparison were conducted using the Tablet device running the benchmark application tool and a data frequency of $10Hz$ and a 5G access technology. The corresponding graphs are presented in Figure 6, following the same pairs of graphs for comparison as presented for the Raspberry Pi tests. The obtained results also confirm in this configuration the advantages of the deployment on the MEC layer, and the performance improvement due to the edge deployment is maintained, with an average delay of $28ms$ compared to $50.1ms$ measured on average for the cloud deployment.

Even in this case, the standard deviation reported in Table I is more constant than the significant mean RTT reduction, leading to the same discussion about the shifting of results from graphs (a), (b) and (c) to (d), (e) and (g), respectively. A comparison between Figure 5 and Figure 6, instead, allows to open a discussion concerning the technologies and the sampling frequencies. The X axes of Figures 6a and 6d are smaller with respect to Figures 5a and 5d, because of the shorter test duration and the lower transmission frequency. Anyway, even comparing different X scales, it is clear that the worst-case samples are reduced significantly in their values and their quantities, also according to Figures 5b and 5e and their counterparts of Figures 6b and 6e, where the worst-case values move from $[300, 350]ms$ to $[175, 200]ms$. As we imputed the worst-case delays of Figure 5 to the access network, previously, changing the access technology to 5G helps reduce it, confirming our description. Continuing, a last observation to Table I reveals that the mean RTT is higher for the 5G tablet with respect to the 4G Raspberry Pi in the MEC scenario: we believe that this counterintuitive difference resides in the different transmission frequencies. Indeed, the Raspberry transmits at $40Hz$ while the Tablet only at $10Hz$; this four-time difference can be translated in harder keep-alive maintenance of the connection with the base station, justifying a higher mean RTT for the 5G Tablet. We aim to investigate this phenomenon in more detail in future works.

To understand the distribution of samples and the corresponding delay measurements based on position along the path

in the MASA test area, the graphs in Figure 7 present the mobility delay results using the Raspberry Pi and associated with GPS positions of each sample. In this configuration, we adopted this specific device, which has higher precision and frequency sampling for the detection of geographic coordinates. Specifically, Figure 7a shows the geographical distribution of samples with the service deployed in the cloud, while Figure 7b displays the measurements obtained with the service deployed on the MEC. For simplicity and better graphical visualization, three delay threshold groups were identified in both configurations to represent different operational ranges to properly support the VRU application and potentially other mobility services with challenging latency constraints. The first range includes all RTT samples below $50ms$, the second range includes samples between $50ms$ and $100ms$, and the third group includes samples exceeding $100ms$. The goal is to understand how many samples fall within stringent time deadlines and identify problematic geographic points in the experimental area.

The results confirm the trend observed in previous data, showing that the MEC deployment generally offers better performance compared to the Cloud deployment. Visually, it is evident that the number of blue points (indicating lower delays) is significantly higher in the MEC deployment than in the cloud configuration. This graph also highlights some issues encountered in the test area, particularly in critical points marked with red markers, where the delay is consistently above $100ms$. These problematic points are present in both deployment scenarios, Cloud and MEC it is likely related to the network deployment or the specific times when the tests were conducted and may be associated with infrastructure load or radio communication interference at the access network stage impacting those specific geographic areas. This aspect needs to be considered in detail, and we plan to investigate it further in future developments and activities.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this work presented an application that combines 5G networks and MEC computational facilities to process and analyze diverse data sources to build a holistic

view of the road environment and enable effective and intelligent management of VRUs. The application showcases a solution capable of potentially reaching a wide number of users without the need for additional hardware and making the solution cost-effective and deployable in various environments. Initial experimental results show that the use of MEC facilities notably supports the deployment of this kind of application by reducing communication latency between the users and the infrastructure.

Future research and developments will further refine and expand upon the demonstrated capabilities, ensuring the continuous evolution and effectiveness of intelligent services to support vulnerable users in smart cities. In particular, we plan to measure the end-to-end delay between the detection of dangerous situations by the camera and the alert provided to the driver and to conduct more extensive experimental campaigns that also focus on other aspects of the applications: precision and recall of the accident forecast, user acceptance, and scalability.

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